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Trends and Perspectives in E-commerce and Sustainable Consumption: A Bibliometric Overview

Dileep Kumar Singh

Post Doctoral Fellow, Institute of Management & Commerce Srinivas University, Manglore and Assistant Professor
Narsee Monjee Institute of Management Studies (NMIMS) Hyderabad, Telangana
✉ dileep.udai@gmail.com

P. S. Aithal

Professor
Institute of Management & Commerce Srinivas University
Manglore, Karnataka
✉ psaital@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This bibliometric review explores the intricate connection between sustainable consumption and e-commerce by looking at how online platforms affect consumer behavior in a sustainable setting. Using a thorough search approach, we located and examined 720 papers from 395 sources in the Scopus database, covering a wide spectrum of academic contributions from 2000 to 2024. Within this developing discipline, our bibliometric research revealed important topics, authors, and trends. Notably, the motor topic emphasized the importance of technology and decision-making processes in changing the e-commerce environment, highlighting the value of decision support systems, e-commerce quality, trust, and service quality. With the inclusion of social sustainability, supply chain dynamics, sustainable development, neuromarketing, optimization, dependability, and online buying, the developing subject examined the relationship's multifaceted facets. The thematic analysis also uncovered a niche topic that reflected the complexities of contemporary retail operations and was centered on inventory control, omni-channel strategies, resilience, network architecture, and tabu search optimization. The study also included eminent writers, references, and papers that shed light on the state of e-commerce and sustainable consumption research throughout the world.

KEYWORDS: *E-commerce, Sustainable consumption, Bibliometric analysis, Online platforms, Consumer behaviour.*

INTRODUCTION

The traditional retail sector has seen disruptive components brought forth by e-commerce platforms. They provide customers with never-before-seen levels of accessibility and convenience, letting them explore, evaluate, and buy things from the comfort of their homes. Due to the shift in customer behavior toward online buying, there are now fewer geographical obstacles to entry, opening up access to a worldwide marketplace (Zhou et al., 2022). Furthermore, e-commerce's capacity to improve logistics and simplify supply chains may result in efficiencies that lessen the environmental effects of traditional brick and mortar retail. But, in addition to these advantages, there are some noteworthy drawbacks that should be taken into account. The environmental impact

of e-commerce activities is one such worry (Salazar V., 2021). The packing and long-distance shipping of goods can increase trash production and carbon emissions. Important first steps in reducing these effects include putting sustainable packaging solutions into practice, streamlining delivery routes, and looking at alternate modes of transportation (Riasat & Shah, 2021). Furthermore, concerns regarding ethical production methods and responsible sourcing are brought up by the growth of e-commerce. Since the speed at which internet commerce is growing can sometimes mask product origins and production processes, supply chain transparency and traceability must be established (Rakhimberdiev, Ishnazarov, Allayarov, et al., 2022). This is especially important to make sure that products are made in an ecologically conscious manner and under fair labour circumstances (Kaluzhnova et al., 2019).

The emergence of e-commerce offers a chance to encourage and reward the purchase of sustainable goods within the framework of sustainable consumption. Products that follow ethical and ecological manufacturing criteria can be promoted and shown off on online platforms (Rakhimberdiev, Ishnazarov, Khayitova, et al., 2022). Through emphasizing these options and giving customers clear details about the products' materials and origins, e-commerce has the potential to significantly influence sustainable consumption (Shang et al., 2023). Thus, the area where e-commerce and sustainable consumption converge is dynamic and ever-changing, having the potential to have both beneficial and detrimental effects on the world's efforts to achieve sustainability (Ananova, 2018). It is crucial that we critically assess the complexities, trade-offs, and possibilities that emerge as academics and stakeholders continue to investigate this intricate relationship. We can make sure that the digital marketplace adheres to the principles of sustainable consumerism by doing thorough analysis and making educated policy decisions, which will eventually help to create a more equal and balanced global economy (Hoang & Phan, 2022).

In this study, we investigate the complex link that exists between e-commerce and sustainable consumption, with a particular emphasis on the ways that online platforms affect consumer behaviour in respect to sustainability (Hassani et al., 2019). Through a bibliometric analysis of the current literature, we aim to identify important themes, ground-breaking research, and developing trends in this rapidly developing subject (Meenar et al., 2022; Nobre & Tavares, 2021). In order to better understand the complexity of this important nexus, our bibliometric study lays the groundwork for future research directions and policy actions that will promote a more just and sustainable digital economy (Lian & Feng, 2022).

Research Questions

1. What are the predominant research themes and topics within the intersection of e-commerce and sustainable consumption, as revealed by bibliometric analysis?
2. Who are the authors driving research in the field of e-commerce and sustainable consumption?

3. What are the most influential and highly-cited publications in the field of e-commerce and sustainable consumption?
4. Are there discernible geographical patterns in research output and collaboration within the domain of e-commerce and sustainable consumption?

OBJECTIVES

1. To Conduct a bibliometric analysis to identify and analyze the predominant research themes and topics at the intersection of e-commerce and sustainable consumption, unveiling the key areas of focus within the academic literature.
2. To Identify and profile the authors who are prominently contributing to research in the field of e-commerce and sustainable consumption, elucidating their respective roles and influence within the scholarly community.
3. To Determine the most influential and highly-cited publications within the field of e-commerce and sustainable consumption through citation analysis, providing insight into seminal works and their impact on the research landscape.
4. To Investigate geographical patterns in research output and collaboration within the domain of e-commerce and sustainable consumption, discerning trends in publication distribution and the extent of international collaboration among researchers.

METHODOLOGY

For this bibliometric overview, we conducted a comprehensive search using the Scopus database (Popescu et al., 2021) to identify relevant literature at the intersection of e-commerce and sustainable consumption. The search strategy was designed to capture publications that encompassed key terms related to e-commerce (such as "e-commerce," "online marketing," "digital marketing," and "internet marketing") in conjunction with sustainability-related terms ("sustainability," "sustainable," "sustainably").

The inclusion criteria for this study focused on English-language publications to ensure consistency and

accessibility. Additionally, we limited the search to articles, conference papers, and reviews to ensure a focused and scholarly examination of the field.

To further refine the selection, we employed search string as TITLE-ABS-KEY (“e commerce” OR online AND marketing OR “Web Marketing” OR “digital Marketing” OR “internet marketing”) AND (sustainabl*) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , “English”) in Scopus database, which allowed us to target publications with a primary focus on the intersection of e-commerce and sustainable consumption. By ensuring that the papers that were retrieved were pertinent to our study objectives, this strategy improved the bibliometric analysis’s validity and reliability.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Analysis

The dataset spans the years 2000–2024 and includes a wide range of scholarly works that explore the nexus between sustainable consumption and e-commerce. It includes 395 distinct publications, including books, journals, and conference papers, for a total of 720 items. The information shows an annual growth rate of -4.47%, which suggests that throughout the given time period, research output somewhat decreased. The documents’ 3.43-year average age indicates a relatively new and active topic of study. Remarkably, an average of 10.56 citations are obtained for each paper, highlighting the importance and influence of the research conducted in this field. The dataset also includes 4,514 additional indexing phrases in addition to a wide range of keywords from the writers. There are 1,912 distinct writers overall, with 97 documents written by a single author and an average of 3.08 co-authors per document in terms of authorship. 22.36% of the partnerships are international co-authorships, highlighting the worldwide reach of this field’s research. There are many different kinds of documents in the dataset; the most common ones are articles (443), which are followed by conference papers (136), book chapters (64), and reviews (35). This extensive and multifaceted dataset provides insights about collaborative behaviours, document genres, and citation effect, making it an invaluable tool for

comprehending the changing field of e-commerce and sustainable consumption research.

Figure 1: Most Influential Sources

The provided figure 1 offers a comprehensive overview of the sources contributing to research in the field of e-commerce and sustainable consumption. Among the 395 identified sources, “Sustainability” based in Switzerland emerges as the most prolific, with a notable 139 articles. This journal evidently plays a pivotal role in disseminating research at the intersection of e-commerce and sustainable consumption. Following closely are “Lecture Notes in Networks and Systems,” “ACM International Conference Proceeding Series,” and “Environmental Science and Pollution Research,” each contributing significantly with 10, 8, and 8 articles respectively. These sources, along with journals like “Journal of Cleaner Production” and “Lecture Notes in Computer Science,” underscore the multidisciplinary nature of research in this domain, drawing from networks, systems, environmental science, and computer science. Additionally, the dataset encompasses a diverse range of publications, including conference proceedings, case studies, and journals, indicating the varied platforms through which research in e-commerce and sustainable consumption is disseminated. This breadth of sources reflects the dynamic and evolving nature of the field, with contributions from both specialized and interdisciplinary outlets.

Three Field Plot

Figure 2: Three Field Plot

A three-field plot, also known as a Sankey diagram, is a visual representation used to depict flows of resources, energy, or information between three different entities or categories. It consists of three columns or nodes, each representing a distinct category, and flows or arrows connecting them to illustrate the movement or distribution of a quantity from one category to another. The width of the arrows is proportional to the quantity being represented, allowing for a clear visualization of the relative magnitudes of flows between the categories. Figure 1 presents three field plot or Sankey plots which are used to show the relationship between three fields with the size of the part corresponding to the node's value. A three-field plot with the left field as authors, the middle field as keyword plus and right field as sources were configure in the mentioned three-field plot diagram.

Most Prolific Authors

The dataset presents a snapshot of prolific authors contributing to research at the intersection of e-commerce and sustainable consumption. Among the 1,912 unique authors identified, Pratap S emerges as a leading contributor with 9 articles to their name, followed closely by Prajapati D, who has authored 8 articles. These individuals have demonstrated a substantial commitment to producing valuable research in this dynamic field. Additionally, authors like Buldeo Rai H, Tumino A, Callou G, and Maciel P have each contributed significantly with 7 or 6 articles, indicating a notable level of expertise and dedication to advancing

knowledge in this domain. The presence of multiple authors with a substantial number of contributions underscores the collaborative nature of research in this field. This diversity of authorship suggests a rich and varied pool of expertise, contributing to the multidisciplinary and evolving nature of research at the nexus of e-commerce and sustainable consumption.

Figure 3: Most Prolific Authors

Table 1: Most Influential Documents

S.NO	Document	Year	Local Citations	Global Citations	LC/GC Ratio (%)
1	VELAZQUEZ R, 2019, IEEE INT CONF IND ENG ENG MANAGE	2019	4	12	33.33
2	AHMADI E, 2021, IEEE INT CONF IND ENG ENG MANAG, IEEM	2021	2	3	66.67
3	TIWAPAT N, 2018, IEEE INT CONF INTELL TRANSP ENG, ICITE	2018	2	15	13.33
4	CALLOU G, 2013, COMPUT	2013	2	31	6.45
5	SETTEY T, 2021, SUSTAINABILITY	2021	1	25	4.00
6	WANG C-N, 2021, AXIOMS	2021	1	44	2.27
7	KUMAR G, 2020, SUSTAINABLE CITIES SOC	2020	1	57	1.75
8	PATELLA SM, 2021, SUSTAINABILITY	2021	1	51	1.96
9	HAN C, 2020, SUSTAINABILITY	2020	1	9	11.11
10	XIAO L, 2019, SUSTAINABILITY	2019	1	80	1.25

The table provides a list of highly cited documents within the context of e-commerce and sustainable consumption. These documents have been influential within their respective years of publication and have garnered notable recognition both locally and globally. For instance, the work by Velazquez R, presented at the IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management in 2019, received 4 local citations and 12 global citations, resulting in a local citation to global citation ratio of 33.33%. Similarly, Ahmadi E's contribution at the 2021 IEEE International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Engineering Management received 2 local citations and 3 global citations, resulting in a high local citation to global citation ratio of 66.67%. The data further showcases the impact of other notable documents, with varying degrees of local and global citations. Tiwapat N's work in the 2018 IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Engineering garnered 2 local

citations and 15 global citations, demonstrating a local citation to global citation ratio of 13.33%. Callou G's paper from 2013 in the journal "Comput" received 2 local citations and an impressive 31 global citations, resulting in a local citation to global citation ratio of 6.45%. These ratios provide insights into the relative influence of these documents within the academic community.

Bibliographic Coupling of Countries

The figure 4 represents bibliographic coupling (Marrucci et al., 2022) between countries in the context of e-commerce and sustainable consumption research. China emerges as a prominent contributor with 116 documents, accompanied by a substantial citation count of 1460. This highlights China's significant presence in this research domain, indicating a robust academic output and influence. Following closely, India exhibits noteworthy contributions with 71 documents and 461 citations, underlining its active engagement in this field. The United States and Italy also feature prominently, each producing 70 documents, with citation counts of 1431 and 958 respectively. This suggests a strong research presence and impact from these countries. Furthermore, the United Kingdom and Germany demonstrate substantial involvement with 50 and 37 documents, supported by citation counts of 949 and 697 respectively. These numbers indicate a considerable level of academic engagement and influence in e-commerce and sustainable consumption research. Other countries such as Indonesia, Australia, Spain, and France also make valuable contributions, showcasing a diverse global participation in this dynamic field.

Figure 4: Bibliographic Coupling of Countries

THEMATIC MAPPING

As far as bibliometric analysis is concerned, themes are essential for identifying patterns and trends in a corpus of literature (Uyar et al., 2020). The motor theme denotes the main topic that has been thoroughly studied or investigated, signifying a dominant or major focus in a certain field. Conversely, the overarching topic suggests basic or underlying ideas that function as central themes that are often discussed in the literature. An emerging subject is a topic that is gaining scholarly attention due to its rising or increasing relevance. Even if it's not stated directly, a decline theme might point to a topic that was popular at one point but is currently getting less attention. Through the use of co-occurrence patterns, keyword analysis, and other bibliometric techniques, these themes are found, offering insightful information about the dynamics and course of research in a certain field. It's crucial to keep in mind that how these words are interpreted might change depending on the analysis's context and the bibliometric exploratory techniques used.

Motor Theme

Figure 5 presents a thematic analysis whereby the motor theme—which includes terms like decision support system, e-commerce quality, trust, and service quality—emerges as a crucial emphasis area (Dicaprio et al., 2020). This subject emphasizes how important technology and decision-making procedures are to the e-commerce industry (Thakre et al., 2022). In order to build customer trust, decision support systems are essential to improving the caliber of e-commerce platforms (Yusupova et al., 2020). The focus on service quality highlights how crucial it is to provide a dependable and smooth client experience. This main subject illustrates how technology, processes for establishing trust, and superior customer service interact dynamically to shape the changing e-commerce market and its consequences for sustainable consumption (Belov et al., 2021).

Basic theme

The subject that is emerging encompasses a wide range of terms, suggesting that the link between sustainable consumption and e-commerce is multifaceted. Supply chain, neuromarketing, social sustainability,

sustainable growth, optimization, dependability, and internet purchasing are noteworthy keywords (Duncan, 2022). The growing range of factors at the nexus of sustainability and e-commerce is reflected in this subject. A comprehensive approach to e-commerce that transcends transactional characteristics is indicated by the growing topic, which ranges from the social and environmental implications of sustainable development to the complexities of neuromarketing and optimization (Mohamed & Ali, 2018). In the end, it shapes a more mindful and environmentally friendly environment for online shopping experiences by highlighting the necessity of trustworthy and sustainable practices across the supply chain (Ghaemi Asl et al., 2021; Yawar & Shaw, 2023)

Emerging Theme

As the issue is examined in relation to e-commerce and sustainable consumption, the discussion delves into complex aspects of environmental and logistical concerns. This subject dives into the intricacies of the latter stages of product delivery, highlighting ideas like urban freight, COPERT modeling, last mile delivery, and transport externalities. The focus on last-mile logistics tackles the difficulties and solutions involved in delivering goods straight to customers (Viriyasitvat et al., 2019). The significance of sustainable transportation is further highlighted by COPERT modeling, which assesses emissions and environmental effects. Particularly in urban environments, travel externalities help to provide a thorough knowledge of the wider effects of transportation networks (Bao et al., 2020). Furthermore, the notion of urban freight clarifies the distinct obstacles and prospects presented by electronic trade in highly populated regions. As a cooperative solution, crowd shipping shows how to dynamically optimize last-mile logistics by sharing delivery services (Wilson et al., 2022). This issue is multidimensional and highlights how e-commerce is changing while highlighting how important it is to have effective last-mile delivery options in metropolitan areas (Zhang et al., 2022).

Niche Themes

The discussion dives into advanced tactics to improve resilience and streamline operations while examining a specialized topic within the larger framework of

e-commerce and sustainable consumption (Muminova et al., 2020). Using inventory management strategies denotes a careful approach to controlling stock levels and reducing the possibility of stockouts or overstock. The idea of omni-channel commerce, which emphasizes the integration of several channels for a seamless consumer experience, also touches on this issue (Ertz & Boily, 2019). Network architecture becomes a crucial strategic factor that requires careful supply chain structure planning for optimal performance. An further indication of a dedication to accuracy in decision-making processes is the application of sophisticated optimization techniques like tabu search (Dorofeyev et al., 2018). This specialty subject captures the complexities of contemporary retail operations, where smart network architecture, omni-channel strategies, resilience, and inventory control come together to support the sustainability and adaptation of e-commerce platforms (Sarfraz et al., 2022).

Figure 5 Thematic Map

CONCLUSION

To sum up, this bibliometric analysis offers a thorough grasp of the complex interactions that exist between sustainable consumption and e-commerce. While e-commerce platforms bring with them unparalleled ease for customers, they also present significant environmental issues. Promoting sustainability necessitates addressing problems including ethical production methods, responsible sourcing, and the environmental impact of e-commerce activities. Critical topics emerged from the thematic analysis, such as the rising theme that explores logistical and environmental problems and the motor theme that emphasizes

technology and decision-making. The specialty subject showcased complex methods for improving resilience and streamlining operations. Highly referenced papers, eminent sources, and prolific writers all emphasized how international and diverse this field of study is.

FUTURE RESEARCH SCOPE

Future research opportunities in the dynamic field of e-commerce and sustainable consumption are made possible by the bibliometric analysis that has been given. Academics can investigate in-depth research on particular themes that have been defined, such as the motor theme's emphasis on service quality and decision support systems. More research on the developing topic, in particular on urban freight, COPERT modeling, and last-mile delivery, might offer insightful information on sustainable logistics. Furthermore, the chosen niche issue offers potential for in-depth analyses of contemporary retail operations due to its emphasis on inventory control, omni-channel strategies, and network architecture. Future studies can also examine how patterns of collaboration are changing, how different regions are, and how regulatory changes affect sustainability and e-commerce. The foundation for further investigation and comprehension of the complex link between e-commerce and sustainable consumption is laid by this bibliometric review.

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